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High-fidelity modeling and validation of a wind turbine gearbox

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Abstract. Wind turbine gearboxes are subjected to highly variable and transient operating conditions, resulting in complex internal load paths and vibration phenomena. This paper presents a high-fidelity flexible multibody model of a three-stage wind turbine gearbox. The model combines FE-based and analytical gear contact formulations, lumped bearing stiffness representations, and flexible bodies for the housing and planetary carriers. Validation is performed using long-term operational data from a condition monitoring system (CMS), focusing on frequency-domain spectra and Campbell diagrams derived from housing acceleration measurements. The results show that the model reproduces the dominant gear mesh excitations and the main structural eigenfrequency bands observed in the measurements. The model forms a basis for further model updating and reduced-order modeling for monitoring-oriented applications.

1. Introduction

Wind turbine gearboxes operate under highly variable and transient loading conditions that arise from fluctuating aerodynamic loads, drivetrain dynamics, and control actions. These operating conditions lead to complex load paths and vibration phenomena within the gearbox, making accurate prediction of internal loads and dynamic responses a challenging task. As turbine power ratings continue to increase, these effects become more pronounced, placing higher demands on gearbox durability and reliability.

Although modern gearboxes are extensively engineered and validated, maintenance and replacement remain costly due to the size of the components and the complexity of installation, particularly for offshore applications [1]. As a result, condition monitoring (CM) and predictive maintenance have become essential tools to reduce downtime and optimize maintenance scheduling.

State-of-the-art condition monitoring systems (CMS) primarily rely on generator-side measurements, such as torque, power, and rotational speed, to classify vibration signals measured on the gearbox housing. In this approach, transient torque fluctuations and shock events may be attenuated as they propagate through the drivetrain, which can lead to an underestimation of fatigue damage and limit the accuracy of lifetime predictions [2]. The availability of high-frequency vibration measurements on the gearbox housing opens the possibility for estimating internal load variations. Such high-frequency load information can serve as an additional layer of insight, enabling more advanced CM and predictive maintenance strategies.

High-fidelity multibody (MB) models provide a powerful framework to overcome these limitations by explicitly modeling the dynamic interaction between gears, shafts, bearings, and structural components. The inclusion of structural flexibility is particularly important to capture misalignment effects, load redistribution, and structure-borne vibration phenomena that govern gearbox dynamic behavior. However, constructing such models requires a careful balance between modeling accuracy and computational efficiency.

This paper presents a flexible MB model of a three-stage wind turbine gearbox comprising two planetary stages and one helical stage. The model integrates analytical and FE-based gear contact formulations, lumped bearing stiffness representations and flexible models of the gearbox housing and planetary carriers. Validation is performed using long-term operational condition monitoring system (CMS) data by comparing simulated and measured housing accelerations under nominal operating conditions and across the full operating range.

The main contributions of this work are twofold: (i) the development of a flexible MB model of a multi-megawatt wind turbine gearbox (Section 2), and (ii) an evaluation of the model's capability to reproduce system-level vibration behavior relevant for condition monitoring applications using long-term CMS data (Section 4).

2. Modeling approach

This section presents the modeling strategy adopted to develop a high-fidelity MB model of a wind turbine gearbox. The approach is constructed incrementally, starting from a rigid MB representation and progressively increasing model fidelity by introducing advanced gear contact formulations, bearing stiffness representations, and flexible components. Each modeling choice is motivated by the need to accurately capture load transmission, dynamic excitation, and structural response while maintaining a feasible computational cost. The section first outlines the system layout and general assumptions, followed by the rigid MB formulation, the gear contact modeling strategy, the bearing representation, and finally the integration of flexible bodies for selected gearbox components.

2.1. System overview and modeling assumptions

To obtain an accurate representation of the torque transmitted to the different drivetrain components, a MB gearbox model is developed. The investigated gearbox corresponds to a 6 MW wind turbine and consists of two planetary stages and one helical stage, illustrated in Figure 1. In both planetary stages, the ring gear is fixed to the housing, the planetary carrier acts as the input, and the sun gear is the output, yielding the largest transmission ratio.

2.2. Rigid multibody formulation

All gear geometries are defined using *Siemens Transmission Builder* [3], a tool in *Simcenter 3D Motion*. The shafts and planetary carriers are also included and characterized by their material and inertia properties. At this stage, bearings are represented as joints with one degree of freedom (DOF), while rigid connections are modeled as fixed joints. The resulting assembly of all components in the power path is shown in Figure 3 (left).

2.3. Gear contact modeling

Accurate modeling of the gear contact is essential for predicting load distribution, dynamic excitation, and vibration transmission within the gearbox. In this work, an advanced gear contact formulation available in *Siemens Transmission Builder* is employed, combining FE-based compliance calculations with analytical contact models.

Figure 1. Rendered view of the CAD model of a 6 MW wind turbine gearbox.

The gear contact stiffness is derived using a dedicated FE preprocessor. This preprocessing tool generates detailed FE models of the gear bodies and evaluates their bulk compliance under load. The resulting stiffness and deformation characteristics are stored in a database and subsequently used during the MB simulation to resolve the gear contact forces.

To account for local tooth contact deformation, the bulk compliance obtained from the FE analysis is complemented by analytical expressions based on the classical formulation of Weber and Banaschek [4]. This hybrid approach enables an efficient yet accurate representation of both global gear body flexibility and local contact compliance at the tooth interface.

By combining FE-based bulk compliance with analytical contact stiffness, the adopted gear contact model captures the key mechanisms governing load sharing and dynamic excitation in geared systems, while remaining computationally suitable for system-level time-domain simulations of the complete gearbox.

2.4. Bearing representation

Bearings can be modeled in different ways depending on the required level of detail and computational cost. A commonly used representation is a symmetric 6×6 stiffness and damping matrix, which captures the elastic coupling between the rotating shafts and the gearbox housing. In many practical applications, the off-diagonal terms of this matrix are neglected and only the diagonal stiffness components are retained, as this simplification substantially reduces model complexity while having a limited influence on the global dynamic response of the drivetrain.

The stiffness values used in such formulations are typically derived from analytical bearing models that relate applied loads to bearing deflections based on contact mechanics and bearing geometry. While the accuracy of these linearized models decreases when operating conditions deviate substantially from the selected linearization point, they have been shown to provide sufficiently accurate predictions of bearing load distribution in the vicinity of nominal operating conditions. This modeling strategy is therefore commonly adopted as a standard approach in MB simulations of wind turbine drivetrains and is also followed in the present work, consistent with [5].

More advanced formulations that account for nonlinear load–displacement behavior or transient effects of rolling elements entering and leaving contact exist in the literature, but are not considered in this work, which focuses on system-level effects. While a variable stiffness formulation is adopted for the gear contacts, as they constitute a dominant excitation mechanism at the gear mesh frequencies (GMF), bearing-induced excitations are of secondary importance

for the vibration phenomena of interest. Consequently, a constant-stiffness approach is adopted throughout this work, providing a practical balance between model accuracy and complexity.

2.5. Flexible multibody integration

Accounting for flexibility of key components, leading to gear misalignments, is crucial to construct a high-fidelity gearbox model that accurately captures realistic excitations arising from the gear contact. The gearbox model should be validated with existing accelerometer measurements on the gearbox housing. Therefore, the flexibility of the gearbox housing should be considered to accurately capture local deformation and dynamic response. Moreover, the housing is connected to the ring gear through bolted joints, such that both components must be modeled as flexible bodies to correctly reproduce their coupled dynamics. In addition, the planetary carriers are included as flexible components, as the high torque at the input and their large size make them prone to significant deflections under operating loads. For both the gearbox housing and the planetary carriers, a low modal damping ratio of 0.2% is adopted, consistent with values reported in the literature for wind turbine gearbox components [6].

All flexible components are discretized using second-order tetrahedral finite elements. Appropriate constraint definitions are applied at the connection interfaces to ensure physically consistent load transfer between components. RBE3 elements are used to distribute forces between flexible bodies and bearing connection points, enabling realistic transmission of reaction loads without artificially increasing local stiffness. RBE2 elements are employed where rigid coupling is required, such as at the torque arm interface with the nacelle. At bolted interfaces between housing sections, mesh mating conditions are applied to represent structural continuity. The resulting FE models of the flexible components considered in this work are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. FEM models of planetary carrier 1 (left), planetary carrier 2 (middle), housing (right)

By incorporating these flexible bodies, the MB model can reproduce both the overall dynamic behavior and the local accelerations and stresses observed in practice. The resulting gearbox model assembly, both without and with the flexible housing, is illustrated in Figure 3. Therefore, this flexible representation is a key enabler for validating the model against measurements and for investigating load paths within the gearbox.

3. Measurements

This section provides an overview of the measurement data used for validation of the gearbox model. First, the available signals and their characteristics are described, followed by a summary of the signal processing methods applied for validation.

3.1. Available signals and measurement characteristics

The gearbox model is validated using long-term operational data collected by a CMS over a six-year period. Approximately one measurement set per day is available, yielding a total of about

Figure 3. Gearbox model assembly without housing (left) and with housing (right).

2200 measurement sets. The measured quantities consist of acceleration signals recorded at eight locations on the gearbox housing, as shown in Figure 4. The accelerometers are distributed to capture the dynamic response of the different gearbox stages. On the housing of the first planetary stage, two accelerometers are installed: one measuring in the radial direction and one in the axial direction (hereafter referred to as 1PL R and 1PL A). An identical configuration is used for the second planetary stage.

On the third stage housing, four accelerometers are installed. One radial sensor is located near the third stage low-speed shaft (LSS), while three sensors are positioned near the high-speed shaft (HSS): two on the generator side (one radial and one axial) and one radial sensor closer to the rotor side.

Figure 4. CAD model of the ZF gearbox with accelerometer locations indicated.

Different sampling strategies are used for the planetary and helical stages to cover their respective frequency ranges. The first and second planetary stages are sampled at 2560 Hz with a record length of 6.4 s (16,384 samples). For the third stage, a higher sampling frequency of 12,800 Hz is used to capture the higher characteristic frequencies, resulting in a shorter record length of 1.28 s for the same number of samples.

In addition to the acceleration signals, each measurement is associated with the mean generator speed and the active power at the time of acquisition. These signals will be used later to sort the measurements to construct Campbell diagrams.

3.2. Processing of measurement data

For model validation, the time-domain signals are transformed into the frequency domain using spectral analysis. For the first and second planetary stages, frequency spectra are computed up to 1 kHz using a Hanning window, with a low-frequency cutoff of 1 Hz. For the third stage, spectra are computed up to 5 kHz using a Hanning window, with a low-frequency cutoff of 8 Hz.

To construct Campbell diagrams, all measurements are ordered according to increasing rotational speed. The resulting frequency spectra are then plotted sequentially, with color scaling used to indicate the acceleration amplitude. These Campbell diagrams are presented in the model validation section and compared with speed ramp-up simulations from the MB gearbox model.

4. Model validation

The gearbox model is validated using two complementary approaches. First, the simulated frequency spectra are compared with measurements under nominal operating conditions of the wind turbine to assess how well gear mesh excitations are reproduced. Second, Campbell diagrams are used to compare the system eigenfrequencies and structural resonances.

Although the measured acceleration signals for the third stage contain frequency content up to 5 kHz, the analysis bandwidth in the simulations is intentionally limited. For the comparison of individual frequency spectra, the simulated results are evaluated up to 2.5 kHz, as this range fully captures the relevant gear mesh frequency of the third stage and its dominant harmonics. Above this frequency, both the measured and simulated responses exhibit significantly lower amplitude levels, indicating a limited contribution to the overall vibration energy and to the validation objectives of this study.

4.1. Comparison of frequency spectra

The torque input for the simulations is derived from measured generator active power P and rotational speed ω according to $T = \frac{P}{\omega}$. These operating conditions are applied to the MB model, which computes the resulting rotational speeds, gear contact forces and housing accelerations.

Simulated and measured accelerations are compared in the frequency domain to identify characteristic spectral components associated with gear mesh frequencies and structural resonances. It is important to note that a single simulation at nominal operating conditions was used for all comparisons. The measured spectra originate from eight accelerometers that are recorded sequentially during a one-minute CMS acquisition. Although the turbine operated close to nominal conditions during this period, the rotational speed was not perfectly constant. As a result, small variations in the instantaneous speed lead to minor shifts in the measured peak frequencies between different sensor locations.

In the following analysis, the spectra at each accelerometer position are examined with respect to their dominant frequency peaks and harmonic content, the corresponding amplitude levels, and the association of these spectral features with specific gearbox components and excitation mechanisms.

Figure 5 shows the frequency spectrum for the high-speed shaft (rotor-side radial accelerometer). The most prominent peak at 780.6 Hz corresponds to the GMF of the third (parallel) stage. The amplitude levels between simulation and measurement show very good agreement. Multiples of this frequency, representing the second and third harmonics, are also visible, although the third harmonic is significantly lower in the simulation. A component at 112 Hz, corresponding to the GMF of the second planetary stage, is clearly measured, but only its higher harmonics are captured in the simulation at this sensor location.

Figure 6 shows the axial acceleration on the first planetary stage. The simulated amplitudes are approximately three times smaller than measured. During the measurement, the rotational speed was slightly lower than in the simulated case, which explains the minor shift in the peak frequencies. The GMF of the second planetary stage is clearly visible in both datasets, indicating the model captures the main dynamic excitations.

Figure 5. Frequency spectrum comparison for the high-speed shaft (rotor-side radial acceleration): measurement (left) and simulation (right).

Figure 6. Frequency spectrum comparison for the first planetary stage (axial acceleration): measurement (left) and simulation (right).

Figure 7 presents the radial acceleration near the low-speed shaft. The measured amplitudes are roughly twice as high as the simulated ones. The first peak is less pronounced in the simulation, while the second and third peaks are reasonably well reproduced.

It should be noted that the present validation is performed using an open-loop simulation, in which the model parameters were not tuned to match the measurement data. As a result, discrepancies in vibration amplitude and resonance bandwidth are expected and primarily reflect uncertainties in damping parameters and excitation mechanisms.

4.2. Comparison of Campbell diagrams

The Campbell diagrams derived from measurements and simulations are constructed using different approaches. For the measurements, each frequency spectrum corresponds to a quasi-static operating condition characterized by a specific rotational speed and torque. The large number of available measurements allows these spectra to be ordered and plotted sequentially as a function of speed. In contrast, simulating a large number of individual quasi-static operating points is computationally inefficient. Therefore, a speed ramp-up is applied in the MB simulation to generate a continuous Campbell diagram.

The Campbell diagram analysis focuses on frequencies up to 1 kHz, which is sufficient to capture the dominant system eigenmodes governing the global dynamic behavior of the gearbox. At higher frequencies, the response is increasingly dominated by local structural modes, which are of secondary relevance for the system-level vibration mechanisms considered in this study. Consequently, restricting the modal content to 1 kHz allows the use of a larger simulation time

Figure 7. Frequency spectrum comparison for the low-speed shaft (radial acceleration): measurement (left) and simulation (right).

step, substantially reducing the computational effort while retaining the dynamic phenomena of interest.

Figure 8 shows the Campbell diagrams obtained from the measured acceleration signals for the four sensor locations on the planetary stages. Several characteristic features can be identified. Diagonal lines correspond to GMFs and their harmonics, while bearing roller passing frequencies are also visible at lower amplitude levels, often accompanied by multiple harmonics.

Figure 8. Campbell diagrams obtained from the measured acceleration signals for the four sensor locations on the planetary stages.

In addition, horizontal bands indicate structural eigenfrequencies of the gearbox that are largely independent of rotational speed. These eigenfrequencies appear in different frequency regions depending on the sensor location. For all sensors, increased response levels are observed around approximately 100 Hz and 300 Hz. In the frequency range between 600 and 800 Hz, a broader band is visible, which suggests the presence of multiple structural modes occurring in close proximity.

Figure 9 shows the Campbell diagram obtained from the speed ramp-up simulation for the same sensor locations. As in the measurements, the diagonal lines correspond to GMFs and their harmonics. Compared to the measured data, a larger number of harmonics is visible in the simulated results. Bearing roller passing frequencies are not present in the simulation, which is consistent with the use of a constant-stiffness bearing representation.

With respect to the structural eigenfrequencies, the simulated Campbell diagram also shows horizontal bands corresponding to structural modes of the gearbox. These simulated eigenfre-

Figure 9. Campbell diagrams obtained from the multibody model simulation for the same sensor locations.

quencies can be associated with the measured frequency regions. In particular, a structural band around 300 Hz is present in both the measurements and the simulations. Furthermore, the frequency region between 600 and 800 Hz also suggests the presence of multiple closely spaced structural modes in the simulation.

The structural mode observed around 100 Hz in the measurements is not present in the simulation. This discrepancy can be explained by the modeling assumption in which the torque arm is clamped without the use of bushings. The mode observed in the measurements is therefore likely related to a torsional mode of the torque arm assembly, which typically occurs in this frequency range.

In the simulations, these eigenfrequencies are primarily excited when crossed by kinematic orders, whereas outside these crossings their response level remains limited. This behavior is consistent with the relatively high numerical damping adopted in the model and the absence of broadband excitation. In contrast, the measured data show persistent excitation of these modes, which can be attributed to lower effective damping in the real system and the presence of stochastic excitations such as impacts and load fluctuations.

5. Conclusion

This paper presented a high-fidelity flexible MB model of a wind turbine gearbox comprising two planetary stages and one helical stage. By combining advanced gear contact formulations with flexible representations of the gearbox housing and planetary carriers, the model captures key mechanisms governing load transmission, misalignment effects, and vibration response under operational conditions.

Validation against long-term operational measurement data shows that the model reproduces the dominant gear mesh frequencies (GMFs) and their harmonics. Differences in response amplitude were observed, with the simulations occasionally underestimating or overestimating the measured levels. Comparison of the Campbell diagrams further indicates that the model captures the main structural eigenfrequency bands of the gearbox housing. The lowest eigenmode observed in the measurements is not reproduced in the simulation, which can be attributed to the modeling assumption in which the torque arm is clamped without the use of bushings.

The results demonstrate that incorporating structural flexibility is essential for reproducing gearbox dynamics and housing vibrations. While the model captures the dominant excita-

tion mechanisms and structural response patterns, quantitative differences remain in vibration amplitudes and resonance bandwidths. These discrepancies are partly attributed to simplified damping representations and the absence of stochastic excitation mechanisms. Since the present validation is performed in an open-loop configuration, future work will focus on model updating techniques and parameter identification to improve the quantitative agreement with operational measurements across a wider range of operating conditions. In addition, it supports the development of monitoring-oriented models aimed at advanced condition monitoring and predictive maintenance strategies for wind turbine gearboxes.

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